

Nomenclatural novelties in Malvaceae

Rajeev Kumar Singh

Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AIIMS Road, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

E-mail: rksbsiadsingh@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0136-9243>

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Abstract: Replacement names *Dombeya bakeri* R.Kr.Singh and *Malvaviscus sangeetae* R.Kr.Singh are proposed here for the illegitimate names *Dombeya acerifolia* Baker and *Malvaviscus lanceolatus* Rose, respectively. Additionally, to stabilize the application of the name *Dombeya acerifolia* Baker, a lectotype is designated here.

Keywords: *Dombeya acerifolia*, Endemic, Lectotype, Madagascar, *Malvaviscus lanceolatus*, Mexico

Introduction

Dombeya Cav. comprises about 197 species, distributed in tropical Africa, West Indian Ocean and Arabian Peninsula (POWO, 2025). In Madagascar alone, the genus is particularly diverse, represented by 165 species, of which 161 are endemic (POWO, 2025). However, the name *D. acerifolia* Baker (J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 22: 449. 1887) is illegitimate under Article 53.1 of the Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018), as it is a later homonym of *D. acerifolia* (L.) Gaertn. (Fruct. Sem. Pl. 2: 260. 1791). Therefore, a replacement name is proposed here. Furthermore, the lectotype for the name *D. acerifolia* Baker is designated herein to establish its identity and prevent any further misapplication of the name.

Malvaviscus Fabr. is represented by 11 species [*M. achanoides* (Turcz.) Fryxell, *M. arboreus* Dill. ex Cav., *M. concinnus* Kunth, *M. elegans* Linden & Planch., *M. lanceolatus* Rose, *M. oaxacanus* Standl., *M. palmanus* Pittier & Donn.Sm., *M. palmatus* Ulbr., *M. penduliflorus* Moc. & Sessé ex DC., *M. urticifolius* (C.Presl) Fryxell and *M. williamsii* Ulbr.], distributed in tropical and subtropical America (POWO, 2025). In Mexico, the genus consist of 6 species, namely *M. achanoides*, *M. arboreus*, *M. lanceolatus*, *M. oaxacanus*, *M. penduliflorus* and *M. urticifolius*, of which *M. lanceolatus* and *M. oaxacanus* are endemic (POWO, 2025). However, the name *M. lanceolatus* Rose (Contr. U.S. Natl. Herb. 5: 175. 1897) is illegitimate, because it is a later homonym of *M. lanceolatus* Jacques (Ann. Fl. Pomone ser. 2, 2: 346. 1844). Therefore, a replacement name is herein proposed.

Figure 1: Lectotype of *Dombeya acerifolia* Baker (K000241138, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Figure 2: Isolectotype of *Dombeya acerifolia* Baker (K000241137, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Figure 3: Holotype of *Malva viscosa lanceolata* Rose (US00098054, © United States National Herbarium, Smithsonian Institution)

Figure 4: Isotype of *Malvaviscus lanceolatus* Rose (GH00052948, © The Gray Herbarium)

Figure 5: Isotype of *Malvaviscus lanceolatus* Rose (GH00052949, © The Gray Herbarium)

Figure 6: Coloured illustration of *Malvaviscus lanceolatus* Rose

Figure 7: Herbarium specimen of *Dombeya acerifolia* Baker (K006341505, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Nomenclature

Dombeya bakeri R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Dombeya acerifolia* Baker, J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 22: 449. 1887, *nom. illeg., non* (L.) Gaertn., Fruct. Sem. Pl. 2(2): 260. 1791.

Lectotype (designated here): Madagascar, Central Madagascar, *s.d.*, *R. Baron 3446* (K000241138!, Figure 1); isolectotypes K000241137! (Figure 2), P00037283!, P00037284!, P00037285!.

Distribution: Endemic to Madagascar.

Etymology: Named after J.G. Baker (1834–1920), British Botanist.

Notes: J.G. Baker's types are known to be housed at K and WELT. Two specimens corresponding to the name *Dombeya acerifolia* Baker were located at K (K000241137 and K000241138). Among these, the better-preserved specimen K000241138 is here designated as the lectotype as it agrees well with the protologue.

Malvaviscus sangeetae R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Malvaviscus lanceolatus* Rose, Contr. U.S. Natl. Herb. 5: 175. 1897, *nom. illeg., non* Jacques, Ann. Fl. Pomone ser. 2, 2: 346. 1844.

Holotype: Mexico, Chiapas, near Chicharras, 6000 ft., 12–15 February 1896, *E.W. Nelson 3807* (US00098054!, Figure 3); isotypes GH00052948! (Figure 4), GH00052949! (Figure 5).

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico (Chiapas, Colima, Guerrero, Jalisco, Morelos, Nayarit, Oaxaca, Puebla and Veracruz).

Etymology: The species is named in honour of my wife, Sangeeta Singh, whose unwavering support and encouragement have been invaluable to my botanical research.

Notes: A specimen accurately identified as *Malvaviscus lanceolatus* Rose (Figure 6) by P. Fryxell is housed at Kew (K006341505, Figure 7).

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